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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

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Rig Veda and Astronomy

Girish V.¹

Ancient Sanskrit Literature, especially the Rigveda contains a great deal of Astronomical facts hidden in its hymns. The hymns in Vedas is not just poetry but a treasure of knowledge (Vedas means knowledge) on various sciences, psychology and cosmology. It can be very well noted that Astronomy (सिद्धान्त ज्योतिषम्) and astrology (फलित ज्योतिषम्) combined together called ज्योतिषम् is one of the six subsidiary sciences, of the Vedas (वेदानाम्) the others being phonetics (शिक्षा), ritual (कल्पम्), etymology (निरुक्तम्), grammar (व्याकरणम्) and metrics (छन्दस्). This article throws some light on hymns in Rigveda which can be interpreted to the theories in modern astronomy.

Definition of Cosmic Universe in Purusha Sukta

Purusha sukta (पुरुषसूक्तम्) is hymn 10.90 of the Rigveda, dedicated to the Purusha, the “Cosmic Being”. The Purusha Sukta gives a description of the spiritual unity of the universe. It presents the nature of Purusha, or the cosmic being, as both immanent in the manifested world and yet transcendent to it.

The Purusha as defined in the first verse (10.90.1) of the Sukta can be compared to the celestial universe. The Hymn is stated below.

सहस्रशीर्षा पुरुषः सहस्राक्षः सहस्रपात् ।
स भूमिं विश्वतो वृत्वात्यतिष्ठद्दशाङ्गुलम् ॥
सहस्रशीर्षा पुरुषः सहस्राक्षः सहस्रपात् ।
स भूमिं विश्वतो वृत्वात्यतिष्ठद्दशाङ्गुलम् ॥

Taking the meaning of Sahasra as great, the verse defines 5 circles (शीर्षा वृत्तम्, अक्ष वृत्तम्, पाद वृत्तम्, भूमिं वृत्तम्, विश्व वृत्तम्) and the infinite universe (अत्यतिष्ठद्दशाङ्गुलम्) which can be compared to the five great circles and the

1 Research scholar in the Department of Sanskrit Nyaya, SSUS Kalady.

celestial sphere in modern astrophysics.

1. Prime Meridian (शीर्षा वृत्तम्): The great circle on the celestial sphere that passes through zenith, nadir, East, and West points is known as the Prime Meridian. The prime meridian is also mentioned in Surya Siddhanta.

2. Observer's meridian (अक्ष वृत्तम्): The great circle on the celestial sphere which passes through the Poles, Zenith and Nadir points is known as the Observer's Meridian. The Observer's Meridian is divided into:

- a. Upper Observer's Meridian; passes through the Poles and Zenith point
- b. Lower Observer's Meridian; passes through the Poles and Nadir

3. Horizon circle (पाद वृत्तम्): The great circle on the celestial sphere which is perpendicular to the line joining the Zenith and Nadir points is known as the horizon circle.

4. Celestial Equator (भूमि वृत्तम्): The great circle on the celestial sphere which is perpendicular to the axis of rotation is known as the celestial equator.

5. Ecliptic (विश्व वृत्तम्): It is the apparent annual path of the Sun among the stars. It is a great circle inclined to the Equinoctial by about $23^{\circ}.5$; and intersects the Equinoctial in two points; Vernal Equinox (γ) and Autumnal Equinox.

Figure 1: Celestial Sphere with 5 great circles

6. Celestial Sphere (अत्यतिष्ठदृशाङ्गुलम्): All heavenly bodies are moving on the inner surface of an imaginary huge sphere, centred at the earth's centre and of radius infinity.

Speed of Light, Moons and Wheel of time mentioned in Rigveda Bhashya of Sayana

Sayanacharya (died in 1387) was a Sanskrit Mimamsa scholar from the Vijayanagara Empire of South India, flourished under King Bukka Raya. More than a hundred works are attributed to him, among which are commentaries on nearly all parts of the Vedas. In his work Rigveda Bhashya he has defined the speed of light in bhashya for hymn 1-50-4, reconciliation of lunar year and solar year in 1-25-8 and wheel of time in 1-164-11.

Speed of light

The Rig Veda hymn(1-50-4) is as below

तरणिविश्वदर्शतो ज्योतिष्कृदसि सूर्य । विश्वमा भासि रोचनम् ॥

Meaning – You (Sūrya), exceed all in speed; you are visible to all; you are the source of light; you shine throughout the entire space.

For this Sayana has given the commentary as below.

तथा च स्मर्यते-य- जनाना सहस्रे द्वे-द्वे शते द्वे च योजने । एकेन निमिषार्धेन क्रममान नमोस्तु ॥

Meaning - Thus it is remembered: [O Sun] you who traverse 2,202 yojanas in half a nimisha.

1 yojana is about 9 miles (Vishnu Purana Book 1 Chapter 6 p:45:6) and 1 Nimisha as defined in Mahabharata Adiparva is about 0.2133 sec (A nimisha is defined as a blink of the eye). So the speed is calculated as 2202*9 miles / 0.105 sec which is approximately 185793.75 miles/sec. According to modern physicists the speed of light was first discovered in 1676 by Danish astronomer Ole Roemer (1644–1710) which is approximately 186282.397 miles/sec.

The lunar and solar years

The Rig Veda hymn(1-25-8) is as below

वेद मासो धृतव्रतो द्वादश प्रजावतः । वेदा य उपजायते ॥

Meaning - He (Varuna, this hymn is dedicated to Lord Varuna) knows the twelve moons with their progeny: He knows the moon

of later birth.

For this Hymn, Sayana in his bashya states

यः त्रयोदशो अधिकमास उपजायते संवत्सरसमीपे स्वयम् एवोत्पद्यते |

This is a direct reference to the twelve 29.5 day months (period from full/new moon to next full/new moon) of a normal lunar year (354 days) and the 13th additional month added periodically to reconcile the above lunar year with the solar year of 365 days.

The length of the solar year is also hidden in Rig veda Hymn 3-9-9. The hymn

त्रीणि शता ली सहस्राण्यग्निं त्रिंशच्च देवा नव चासपर्यन् । औक्षन्वृतैरस्तृणन्बर्हिरस्मा
आदिद्भोतारं न्यसादयन्त ॥

Meaning - Three thousand three hundred and thirty-nine divinities have worshipped Agni; they have sprinkled him with melted butter; they have spread for him the sacred grass; and have seated him upon it as their ministrant priest.

The hymn mentions about the magic number 3339 which has great significance in astronomy. In the basic vedic unit of 33 years, there are 371 intercalary days, so that in 9×33 that is 297 year period the number of intercalary days is 3339. So in a 297 lunar year of 354 days period, 3339 intercalary days have to be added to get 297 solar years. So if a year starts with full moon/new moon, after 297 year cycle, the year will again start with full/new moon. So the length of the solar year by this calculation is 354 (lunar year days) + (3339/297) which is 354+11.2424 and that is 365.2424 days.

Wheel of Time

Rigveda hymn 1-164-11 talks about the wheel of time.

द्वादशारं नहि तज्जराय वर्वर्ति चक्रं परि द्यामृतस्य ।

आ पुल्ला अग्ने मिथुनासो अत्र सप्त शतानि विंशतिश्च तस्थुः ॥

Meaning: The twelve-spoked wheel, of the true (sun) revolves round the heavens, and never (tends) to decay; seven hundred and twenty children in pairs, Agni, abide in it.

The 12 spoked wheel means 12 sign of zodiac. It can also mean the twelve months of the year. Seven hundred and twenty children in pairs means 360 nights and days.

Conclusion

An astronomical basis of the Rig Vedic organization helps us see Vedic ritual in a new light and it shows the inadequacy of earlier interpretations. We can conclude that Astronomy played a central role in Vedic culture of ancient times. We can also draw parallels between ancient Indian and other astronomical systems. Our solar division of Zodiac into 12 parts is common among Chinese and Greeks. Again our names of the five planets and the names of the days of the week have commonality amongst the Greeks. Also the ceremonies and rituals that we celebrate even today based on times for the full moon/new moon reveal that there existed several traditions of astronomical wisdom. It is evident that people of the Vedic age knew the astronomical science in depth and have encoded the same in form of hymns and rituals.

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Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com